

Terraforming and Constructing Habitats:

A Chart's Presentation
(Extended)

(The numbers and data presented in this table are approximations)

Nr.	Territory	Surface Area compared to Earth	Period of Time	Number of (potentially) hosted people	Company (Ndoni Advanced Robotics) N.A.R	Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats
1.	Moon	0.07	22 nd Century	560M+	N.A.R	30M+
2.	Mars	0.38	23 rd Century	2.5B+	N.A.R	70M+
3.	Saturn	83	24 th -25 th Century	600B+	N.A.R	120B+
4.	Jupiter	120	27 th -30 th Century	900B+	N.A.R	350B+
5.	Solar System	Unspecified	27 th -34 th	50T+	N.A.R	500B+
6.	Milky Way galaxy	Unspecified	1M+ (year)	1.6 Sextillion (160 billion billion)	N.A.R	1 Quintillion -1 Septillion

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